

Local industrial symbiosis in the wood construction value chain

Industrial symbiosis is a collaborative network of diverse organisations that can foster eco-innovations and long-term business culture development, create and share mutually profitable transactions, acquire services and improve business and technical processes together. A local industry park in Northern Finland is a good example of long-term collaboration and partnership between 15 private companies and a municipal RTDI unit. The primary and secondary products produced form a wood construction value chain, where side streams, excess materials and energy are aligned in the context of the bio-circular economy. The network covers sawn timber, planed wood and components, planar and space elements, CLT panels, elements and modular units, log houses and windows. A construction company, design services, CHP plant, pellet factory and three manufacturers of value-added products from wood-based side streams complete the network. The municipal unit supports the industries by organising education and special courses, providing a practical training environment for woodworking and establishing collaborative RTDI projects to accelerate innovations. It also runs the Triple Helix network of the companies, research institutes, schools and universities involved.

Regional coverage and transferability

Local industrial symbiosis is a way to overcome the challenges of remote location from the main markets and customers for individual companies here specifically in the wood construction value chains by providing an efficient material and energy network. Market competitiveness, product and technology development, eco-design, branding and adoption of regulation and cascading ideas for circular bio-economy is reinforced and benefit from local collaboration and endorses investments and fund raising. The local industrial symbiosis is a concept that is highly transferable across all European regions.

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Local sources of raw materials and high utilisation rate of side streams contribute strongly to the circular economy concept and the sustainable use of biomass
- ▶ An integrated industrial park provides to a network of companies a strategic and functional platform for business cooperation and marketing initiatives in the circular bio-economy, especially for SMEs.
- ▶ Networking between primary and downstream processing companies, side stream producers and users enables to integrate research partners for strengthening RTDI activities
- ▶ Opportunities for high-level optimisation of products and side stream utilisation leads to high resource and energy efficiency as well as to closed material and energy loops.
- ▶ Foresight of and flexible adaptation to legislative changes can be achieved in due course.